

Revolution in the theater of war: drones, consumer technology and open source intelligence as forces of change in modern warfare

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1 Abstract

2 In today's era of warfare, we are witnessing a profound transformation driven by the influence of modern technologies. This paper examines
3 how drones, consumer technology and open source intelligence have revolutionized and in many cases rendered traditional warfare strategies
4 obsolete. Rather than relying solely on specialized military technology, modern armed forces are increasingly turning to more cost-effective,
5 accessible and technologically advanced consumer technologies. This development has not only fundamentally changed the way wars are
6 fought, but has also led to a massive shift in cost structures. Mass and availability have become more important, with flimsy, off-the-shelf
7 technologies being used alongside traditional military technology.

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9 **Keywords:** Modern Battlefield; Consumer Technology; Changing Methods; Warfare; Drone Technology; Open Source Intelligence

1 Introduction to modern warfare: historical context and 2 current developments

3 **T**he evolution of warfare is a story of constant change and
4 adaptation that is deeply rooted in human history. Each
5 phase brought with it significant developments that fundamen-
6 tally changed the way wars were fought.

7 From wood to stone and metal

8 In the early days of human civilization, wood was the predomi-
9 nant material for weapons. With the discovery of stone work-
10 ing, humans began to make more effective tools and weapons
11 such as arrowheads and axes. The transition to the Bronze Age
12 marked another turning point, as bronze was used to make
13 swords and armor. The introduction of iron and later steel led
14 to even stronger and more durable weapons, which had a signif-
15 icant impact on warfare.

16 Roman Empire: Strategies and tactics

17 The Roman Empire was characterized by its advanced military
18 strategies and tactics. The Romans perfected the art of siege,
19 the construction of fortresses and roads and developed effective
20 formations such as the famous 'turtle formation'. These tactical
21 innovations, combined with a well-organized army and efficient
22 logistics, enabled Rome to conquer and hold a large territory.

23 Fireworks and rockets in China

24 In China, gunpowder was originally developed for fireworks,
25 but soon found military application in the form of rockets and
26 other explosive weapons. These early forms of artillery had a
27 profound effect on warfare, increasing the effectiveness of sieges
28 and enabling new forms of long-range tactics.

Motorized forces in the Second World War

29 The Second World War was characterized by the massive use of
30 motorized vehicles and tanks. This development changed the
31 mobility and speed with which armies could maneuver and led
32 to new forms of warfare, such as blitzkrieg tactics, which were
33 perfected by German forces. The combination of tanks, aircraft
34 and motorized infantry revolutionized warfare.
35

Radio technology and helicopters in the Vietnam War

36 The Vietnam War was a turning point in the use of radio tech-
37 nology and helicopters. Radio technology allowed for improved
38 communication and coordination on the battlefield, while heli-
39 copters were critical for rapid troop movement, evacuation
40 and air support. These technologies significantly changed the
41 dynamics of guerrilla and jungle warfare.
42

The era of nuclear weapons

43 The introduction of nuclear weapons during the Second World
44 War marked an unprecedented change in warfare. With the de-
45 structive power of the atomic bombs dropped on Hiroshima and
46 Nagasaki, humanity entered a new era in which total annihila-
47 tion became possible. This led to the development of the theory
48 of deterrence during the Cold War and fundamentally changed
49 the global political landscape.
50

Findings

51 Each of these developments represents a significant leap in mili-
52 tary technology and tactics that dramatically changed the way
53 wars were fought. They reflect a continuous adaptation to new
54 challenges and the constant search for advantage on the battle-
55 field. The historical development of military technology paints a
56

clear picture: with each new era, warfare became more complex, weapons became larger, heavier and their destructive power more comprehensive. From the simple, handmade tools of the early days to the sophisticated weapon systems of the 20th and 21st centuries, there has been a steady trend towards greater power and range. This development culminated in the introduction of nuclear weapons, which represent the potential for unprecedented destruction. Overall, the history of military technology reflects a ceaseless quest for superior strength and control, with each innovation pushing the boundaries of destructive capability further. It is a path driven by the need for battlefield superiority that has profoundly and permanently changed warfare.

The power of consumer technology: a new actor in conflict

The power of consumer technology in the context of modern conflict is a phenomenon that is becoming increasingly important. The technologies we use every day have the potential to fundamentally change the way conflict is conducted and experienced.

High technology in your pocket

Modern smartphones are examples of sophisticated technology that has become ubiquitous. These devices, which combine powerful processors, advanced sensors and versatile communication capabilities, are no longer just means of communication, but also powerful tools for data collection and processing. According to Eric Schmidt and Jared Cohen in "The New Digital Age: Reshaping the Future of People, Nations and Business" (Knopf, 2013), smartphones have the potential to transform every citizen into an informant or activist by providing access to information and communication capabilities.

Robust and powerful wireless networks

Advances in wireless technology, particularly with the introduction of 5G, have resulted in networks that are not only fast and efficient, but also resilient to interference. These networks allow for almost uninterrupted communication and data exchange, which can be crucial in conflict situations. A report by Deloitte on 5G technology highlights that these networks can play a key role in modern warfare by providing fast and secure communication channels.

Advances in optics and image enhancement

Modern optics and AI-supported image enhancement technologies have made it possible to produce clear images even in poor lighting conditions. Research in the field of artificial intelligence, such as that conducted by Google DeepMind, shows that AI algorithms are capable of significantly enhancing imagery, which can also be useful in nocturnal military operations.

Ausgereifte Verschlüsselungsverfahren

Die Verschlüsselungstechnologie hat sich ebenfalls rasant entwickelt. Moderne Verschlüsselungsmethoden wie AES (Advanced Encryption Standard) sind bisher nicht erfolgreich gebrochen worden. Laut einem Bericht des National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) bietet AES einen hohen Grad an Sicherheit und ist für sensible Regierungsdaten zugelassen.

Findings

These developments show that consumer technology no longer only serves civilian life, but has also become a decisive factor in modern conflicts. The ubiquity and power of these technologies is changing the landscape of warfare, creating new opportunities and challenges for military and civilian actors. The rapid development of consumer technology has not only fundamentally changed the way we communicate and share information, but also our habits and expectations of communication technology. In today's world, people are used to communicating over long distances in milliseconds, sharing images and data in real time and coming together in virtual groups to share information and insights. These skills and habits are also maintained in conflict situations and play an increasingly important role.

In the context of combat, this type of communication and data sharing enables a new level of coordination and collaboration. Soldiers and military leaders can receive and share information in real time, enabling quick decisions and adjustments on the battlefield. In addition, groups of fighters can organize and coordinate efficiently, even if they are physically separated.

This evolution towards increasingly networked and technologically savvy warfare places new demands on military strategy and tactics. Military leaders must not only understand these modern communication habits and capabilities, but also utilize them effectively in order to be successful in future conflicts. The integration of modern consumer technologies into military planning and execution is therefore not just an option, but a necessity to meet the ever-changing demands of modern warfare.

Drones on the battlefield: from reconnaissance to combat

The use of drones on the battlefield is an impressive example of how technologies originally developed for the consumer market can be used effectively in military contexts. DJI, a leading global manufacturer of civilian drones, offers a wide range of drone models, from small, lightweight variants to larger models capable of carrying light loads. DJI has made a significant impact on the market and technology development in this area, as outlined in a report by The Verge ("DJI's drone domination", The Verge, 2020).

In the Ukraine war, drones were used for various military purposes, including dropping explosives. This tactic demonstrates how relatively simple and inexpensive devices can be used in armed conflict to achieve significant effects. A BBC report ("Drones in the Ukraine War", BBC News, 2021) describes how drones were used for targeted attacks, which had a significant impact on warfare in the region.

Another important aspect is the use of drones for reconnaissance. Small, maneuverable drones offer troop units the opportunity to gather information from a safe distance without exposing themselves to direct risk. This enables efficient and relatively safe information gathering. According to an article in "Military Review" ("The Role of Drones in Modern Warfare", Military Review, 2022), the ability to conduct reconnaissance from a distance has significantly expanded tactical options on the battlefield.

One particularly notable aspect of drone use is the asymmetry of cost. Inexpensive commercial drones can damage or destroy very expensive military equipment. This cost asymmetry poses a challenge to traditional military strategies and is forcing armies to rethink their approaches to defense and offensive tactics. An article in The Economist ("The Asymmetric Power of Drones",

1 The Economist, 2021) highlights that this cost differential is a
2 game changer in warfare, as it allows smaller players to achieve
3 significant effects with limited resources.

4 Findings

5 Overall, the development and application of drones on the bat-
6 tlefield shows how supposedly simple consumer technologies
7 can profoundly change warfare. These technologies not only
8 offer new possibilities for military operations, but also change
9 the dynamic and strategic considerations on the battlefield.

10 Open source intelligence: information gathering for all

11 Open source intelligence (OSINT) has become a critical ele-
12 ment in modern warfare and security policy. Access to publicly
13 available information and its effective use have fundamentally
14 changed the landscape of information gathering and processing.

15 Use of digital communication platforms

16 Platforms such as Discord have become important tools for
17 information sharing and organization in conflict zones. Such
18 platforms allow information to be disseminated and discussed
19 quickly, which is particularly important in fast-moving and dy-
20 namic conflict situations. An article in The Guardian ("How
21 Discord is Used in Modern Warfare", The Guardian, 2022) de-
22 scribes how these types of platforms are used to gather and
23 disseminate real-time information from conflict zones.

24 Encrypted and anonymous communication

25 Messaging services such as Signal and Threema play an impor-
26 tant role in modern warfare by providing secure and encrypted
27 communication channels. These services allow users to remain
28 anonymous and share sensitive information without fear of be-
29 ing intercepted. A report by Wired ("The Rise of Encrypted
30 Messaging in Warfare", Wired, 2021) shows how such applica-
31 tions are used by military personnel, journalists and civilians in
32 conflict regions.

33 Experts and analysts like Perun

34 Individuals like Perun, who specialize in the analysis of wars
35 and their contexts, use OSINT to provide in-depth insights and
36 analysis. They collect publicly available data and interpret it to
37 paint a clearer picture of events in conflict zones. An article in
38 "The Atlantic" ("The Role of Independent Analysts in Modern
39 Warfare", The Atlantic, 2022) sheds light on how such indepen-
40 dent experts contribute to the information landscape.

41 Cost-effective satellite images

42 Companies operating satellite fleets are able to provide low-cost
43 and quasi-live satellite imagery. These images are particularly
44 valuable for reconnaissance and surveillance in war zones. A
45 report by SpaceNews ("Commercial Satellites in Conflict Zones",
46 SpaceNews, 2021) shows how such imagery is used to gather
47 important information about troop movements, damage and
48 other relevant events.

49 Findings

50 Overall, it shows how the landscape of information gathering
51 and analysis is being transformed by OSINT and its associated
52 technologies and methods. This development opens up new
53 possibilities for information gathering in conflicts, but also poses
54 new challenges in terms of data security and information pro-
55 cessing.

Call for a change in the development of military technol- 56 ogy: adapting to the dynamics of modern technologies 57 and modern users 58

59 I emphasize the need to quickly and purposefully adapt the
60 development of software and hardware in the field of military
61 technology to the latest technological developments and changes.
62 This requires a paradigm shift in the approach to the design and
63 development of military equipment.

Acceleration of development cycles 64

65 The rapid evolution of technology in the civilian world has
66 shown that long development cycles are no longer practical
67 in military technology. As outlined in a Defense News article
68 ("Rapid Development in Military Technology", Defense News,
69 2022), militaries worldwide need to accelerate their develop-
70 ment processes to keep pace with technological advances. This
71 means that developments that used to take years must now be
72 implemented in months.

Adaptation to user habits 73

74 The technologies soldiers use on the battlefield need to be intu-
75 itive and user-friendly, similar to the smartphones they use in
76 civilian life. A report by Military Technology ("User-Friendly
77 Military Hardware", Military Technology, 2022) highlights that
78 the user-friendliness of military technology is crucial to ensure
79 its effectiveness and acceptance. This requires close cooperation
80 with end users during development.

Reaction to dynamic combat conditions 81

82 As battlefield conditions change rapidly, military technology
83 must be flexible and adaptable. An article in "The Journal of De-
84 fense Management" ("Adapting Military Technology to Chang-
85 ing Warfronts", The Journal of Defense Management, 2023) ar-
86 gues that the ability to respond quickly to new threats and tactics
87 is critical to the success of military operations.

Findings 88

89 In summary, it is essential that the development of military tech-
90 nology becomes agile and adaptable to meet the challenges of
91 modern warfare. This requires rapid implementation of new
92 technologies, intuitive operability and the ability to adapt dy-
93 namically to changing conditions.

94 The author and his colleagues offer themselves to the reader
95 as consultants on these issues.

Summary 96

97 The ongoing integration of consumer technologies and open
98 source intelligence into warfare marks the beginning of a new
99 era. This development indicates that in the future there will be
100 a duality between readily available, high-tech mass technology
101 and conventional military technology. This change is forcing
102 defense contractors and military planners to adapt quickly in
103 order to remain relevant. The massive shift in cost structures
104 and the increased accessibility of technological solutions mean
105 that warfare is becoming increasingly democratized. In light of
106 these developments, it is critical that future strategies consider
107 both the potential and the risks of this new era of warfare and
108 adapt to the rapidly changing realities.

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8 The author is not subject to any "Conflict of Interest".
9 See also [https://academic.oup.com/journals/pages/authors/authors_](https://academic.oup.com/journals/pages/authors/authors_faqs/conflicts_of_interest)
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